

Codebook

Human-AI Collaboration for Decision-Making in Agile Sprint Planning

Ungarala Sai Krishna Yashwanth

Mihir Singh Thakur

Blekinge Institute of Technology, MSc Software Engineering, 2026

The codebook is organised into three groups corresponding to the three main analytical themes that emerged from the data. Group A covers anchoring codes, Group B covers algorithm aversion codes, and Group C covers trust calibration codes.

Group A: Anchoring Codes

A1: Number-first contamination.

AI tool figure shared before independent team estimation shapes subsequent reasoning. Coded when a participant describes the risk of sharing a number early, or when their own vignette reasoning begins from the AI tool's figure.

Example: P6, 9:54 — “People don't process the AI suggest [sic] 42 as a data point. They process it as a reference.”

A2: Reference-point adjustment.

Participant reasons from the AI tool's figure rather than forming an independent judgement.

Example: P2, 14:36 — “34 out of 42 is 80%. . . I would still shoot for to complete all 42.”

A3: Number withholding (safeguard).

Deliberate practice of keeping the AI tool's figure private until after team estimation.

Example: P7, 17:30 — “I would not present the number before the team has done their own estimates.”

Group B: Algorithm Aversion Codes

B1: Developer authority assertion.

Developer invokes domain expertise to dismiss an AI tool flag without articulating a specific basis.

Example: P2, 17:59 — “I am building a product and I need to be managing people.”

B2: Examine both signals (safeguard).

Facilitator requires both AI tool and developer to articulate their basis before the team decides.

Example: P8, 15:27 — “We got two signals pointing in different directions. Let us spend two minutes making sure we understand both before we move on.”

B3: Pattern match scepticism.

Participant questions whether the AI tool’s historical patterns apply to the current context.

Example: P6, 13:27 — “The AI pattern matching on similar stories can be deeply misleading. A story that looks similar on the surface may be touching a completely different infrastructure.”

B4: Legitimate contextual dismissal.

Override based on a concrete identifiable reason that the AI tool’s evidence does not apply.

Example: P4, 2:19 — “Can you walk me through what you think makes this story different from the ones the tool is drawing on.”

Group C: Trust Calibration Codes

C1: Transparency drives trust.

Trust increases when the AI tool explains the basis for its recommendation.

Example: P6, 22:07 — “The explanation needs to be a sentence, maybe two. That is enough. I do not need the model weights.”

C2: Track record drives trust.

Trust updated by past experience of AI tool accuracy or inaccuracy.

Example: P4, 23:48 — “The tool was seeing something we didn’t give enough credit to. . . historical pattern captures better than individual intuitions.”

C3: Human final authority.

Final commitment decision must remain with the team regardless of AI tool capability.

Example: P9, 13:00 — “We should definitely take the inputs from AI, but human should be the final one to decide.”

C4: Facilitator as mediator.

AI tool informs facilitator before session; facilitator decides what to bring and how to frame it.

Example: P6, 22:32 — “The AI stays outside the planning room. . . It is a research tool for the Scrum Master and not a participant in the planning.”

C5: Contextual applicability assessment.

Trust calibrated by assessing whether AI tool patterns apply to current specific conditions.

Example: P8, 15:18 — “I would check whether the AI was drawing on data from when the team was smaller and the codebase less stable.”

Saturation Table

All twelve codes were established by interview P7. P8 and P9 introduced no new codes.

Code	P1	P2	P3	P4	P5	P6	P7	P8	P9
A1	-	-	X	X	-	X	X	X	-
A2	X	X	-	-	-	-	-	X	-
A3	-	-	X	X	-	X	X	X	-
B1	-	X	-	-	X	X	-	-	X
B2	-	-	-	-	-	-	X	X	-
B3	-	-	-	X	-	X	X	X	-
B4	X	X	-	X	X	X	X	X	X
C1	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	-
C2	-	-	-	X	-	X	X	X	X
C3	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X
C4	-	-	X	X	-	X	X	X	-
C5	-	-	X	-	-	-	X	X	-
New codes	4	1	4	2	0	0	1	0	0